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Rapid discovery and development of enzymes for novel and greener consumer products

Research and Innovation Action (RIA)

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D2.5 – Microfluidic workflows to determine thermostability (public summary)

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There are several reasons for which enzymes with enhanced stability prove advantageous for biotechnological applications¹. To improve enzyme stability, enzymes are subjected to an engineering methodology called directed evolution. However, this methodology is expensive and time-consuming. In RADICALZ, we have attempted to enable a method to assay the stability of enzymes at high temperatures, compatible with a novel technology of enzyme assay that uses microscopic water droplets as surrogate test tubes.

First, we tried unsuccessfully to use a folding-reporting reagent (Sypro Orange) in droplets. Then, we tried using *in vitro* expression at higher temperatures based on the cellular components of *E. coli* with insufficient yield, and *Thermus*, with better yield and compatible with several enzyme activities and microdroplets, but the efficiency was still insufficient to be applied for our purposes². Finally, we developed a reaction mixture with enough sensitivity to carry out enzyme synthesis and assay in droplets starting from a single molecule of DNA. This mixture simplifies operations compared with the state of the art, allows the assay of different enzyme activities and allowed us to differentiate enzyme variants with different specific activity. The introduction of a thermal challenge step post-synthesis allowed us to differentiate several enzymes and variants according to their stability.

References

1. Tokuriki, N., Stricher, F., Serrano, L. & Tawfik, D. S. How protein stability and new functions trade off. *PLoS Comput Biol* **4**, 35–37 (2008).
2. Ribeiro, A. L. J. L. *et al.* Thermostable *in vitro* transcription-translation compatible with microfluidic droplets. *Microb Cell Fact* **23**, 169 (2024).

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